

EDUCATION OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY AS A FOUNDATION IN THE POST-PANDEMIC RECOVERY IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Purpose – *The scope of this study is to validate the importance of circular economy education in Romania.*

Methodology/approach - *The method used to explore the topic is primary data collection approach and documentary analysis. This extensive research used the questionnaire as a tool for collecting respondent's views. The aim of the questionnaire was to outline the knowledge towards circular economy and sustainability.*

Findings – *Among the respondents an average level of knowledge was identified. Education models have to be interactive, adapted to the field of learning and based on collaboration between public and private institutions. Target of the Sustainable Development Goals 4 (SDG 4) develop responsible consumption. Target of the SDG 12 is responsible consumption and production.*

Research limitations/implications – *Future research may determine education models based on the characteristics presented in this paper.*

Practical implications – *Educating consumers would provide information and raise awareness. Hence, the circular model is accepted and a sustainable lifestyle is created.*

Originality/value – *starting point for the development of circular economy education methods*

Key words: *Circular Economy, SDG, Education*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has created considerable challenges that weakened the achievement of the sustainable development goals defined by the 2030 Agenda (Cheng et al., 2021). However, on a more positive note, it has also offered a clean sweep. The world can benefit of this opportunity by considering more sustainable approaches (Leach et al. (2021).

Circular economy is a sustainable approach that supports the objectives of the SDGs. Of the 17 established goals, the circular model contributes to SDG 12 the most (Hofstetter et al., 2021). This goal refers to responsible production and consumption. However, one should distinguish between the goals that the concept influences or is influenced by. Undoubtedly, the implementation of the circular model has a positive impact on responsible production and consumption, but the question is which objectives have to be fulfilled first to successfully implement the model. Accordingly, this paper aims to highlight the importance of SDG 4 (quality education) before the circular economy implementation.

Starting from the premise that responsible consumption is contingent on consumer education, this paper seeks to validate the *importance of circular economy education*. Accordingly, the first objective of the paper is to determine the current level of awareness of the circular economy. The second objective deals with the *characteristics of efficient education models*. Finally, the paper illustrates the relationship between education and circular economy.

Literature Review

Romania is battling to implement circular economy practices. Other European Union (EU) countries are much ahead on all levels and in all fields (Marino and Pariso, 2020). For Romania to reach the level of other EU countries, it has to determine an appropriate legislation, encourage innovative ideas, define long-term solutions and last but not least, educate participants (Vermeşan, Mangău and Tiuc, 2020).

The circular economy (CE) is considered to be a long-term recovery strategy that generates environmental, economic and social advantages (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2020). Unlike the linear economy model, where the products proceed only one direction from the producer to the customer, in the circular economy the goods flow is bidirectional. Thus, products or materials come back to the service provider, product, or part manufacturer. Moreover, the bidirectional movement is carried out as often as possible for each product or material. (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). Consumers play an essential role because they are responsible with returning the products in order to preserve circularity. Therefore, it is fundamental to provide information and education to customers regarding the circular principles (Vehmas et al., 2018).

The importance of education is even included in more current definitions of the term CE. Thus, education is just as relevant as products' design in reaching the circularity of the products (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2019). Education is meant to pass on knowledge, experiences, and values from generation to generation with the intention of ensuring human progress. Because of this, education must be moral to fortify sustainable development. Lack of education leads to less knowledge and diminished understanding of moral principles. Thus, people are tempted to resort to immoral measures and corruption is encouraged. Furthermore, a high level of corruption decreases the degree of economic and human development (Busoi, 2015). Education and technological innovations are the foundation of a social transition towards ecological behavior. It also contributes to the achievement of all sustainable development objectives (Dong et al., 2021).

Consequently, consumer behavior has a vital role in Romania's transition towards circular economy. Only if the consumers behave in line with the defined norms of the circular model, they may benefit of the concept's advantages. However, the biggest impediment is not the lack of desire to behave circular, but the absence of information. Therefore, consumers have to be educated for them to accept business models based on the circular economy (Lakatos et al., 2018).

Methodology

This paper is based on qualitative research. First, a survey, in the form of an online questionnaire, was addressed to people living in Romania. Respondents were chosen randomly. The number of respondents is 201. This research is ongoing, and this paper presents the intermediate results obtained.

The outcomes of the questionnaire were analyzed by a statistical software. Following, based on the documentary analysis, we defined characteristics of efficient education models and designed a framework based on specific targets of SDG 4 and SDG 12.

Results and discussion

The first objective of the study is to distinguish the respondents' level of knowledge and involvement in the CE. According to the survey, about 50 percent of the respondents are aware of the term circular economy, Figure 1. Generally, respondents over 45 years old are familiar with the term. The most informed age category, with 80 percent affirmative responses, is category 55 – 65 years old. Contrarily, the least informed age category is 34 – 44 years old.

Figure 1. Knowledge of the term circular economy

In terms of involvement level, Figure 2, most of respondents are eager to adopt a circular behavior. Age category 55 – 64 years old has the highest level of involvement, not just knowledge. Even though age category 65 or above years knows the circular economy term, it has on average the lowest level of involvement and the most divided opinions. It can be noted that age categories with low degree of knowledge have also a lower degree of involvement. This, however, is not applicable for the youngest generation. Respondents under 18 years old are shown to have an extremely involved circular behavior, even if their knowledge level is average.

Figure 2. Involvement level in Circular Economy

From the length of the boxplots, a similar involvement level can be seen at the two youngest age categories. Even though these categories have an above average involvement level, about 50 percent of the respondents do not know the concept of CE. These categories together refer to Gen Z generation. Likewise, the next two age categories, 25 – 34 and 35 – 44 years old, have a similar involvement level. The means and the length of the boxplots are almost equal. These categories together refer to Millennials generation. In the same way, age categories 45 – 54 years old and 55 – 64 years old have similar involvement pattern. These age categories are Generation X. Consequently, the result indicates

similar involvement level across individual of the same generation. Accordingly, education models should be developed by considering the generation they are addressed to.

Concluding the obtained results can be systematized:

1. Education models must be developed over generations depending on age due to different involvement.
2. Motivating young people under the age of 18 to get involved in education to strengthen the great desire to apply the principles of the circular economy.
3. Application of CE norms in a unified way at the national level by observing the principles of sustainable development.
4. The concept of the circular economy is known by the respondents and there are different implications.
5. The CE concept is intended to be applied by the respondents. The respondents of the questionnaire are willing to join the effort to reduce waste and protect the environment. These objectives are among the objectives of the circular economy.

The characteristics of efficient education models

The second objective of the study seeks to identify the characteristics of efficient education models. The introduction of circular economy lectures in education institutes is essential to encourage the concept and to spread the principles. For the student to better understand the concept, the learning materials should be adapted to the field of study. Furthermore, the collaboration of the educational institutions with the government and practices stimulates the CE mindset and eco-responsible behavior (Serrano-Bedia and Perez-Perez, 2022). Hence, sustainable companies may offer internships or Open Days so that the students learn how the closed-loop model is implemented on different sectors and to see what actual impact consumers' action may have. However, a precondition for this scenario is that companies do have a responsible behavior. Some scholars point out that the role of private sector is even more important than the role of the education institutes in developing the concept (Kirchherr and Piscicelli, 2019). In addition, the use of games as educational tools can aid the recognition of relevant actions. The dedicated boardgame determine participants to become aware of problems such as solutions raised by the CE (Whalen et al., 2018). Beside the traditional courses, the introduction of more interactive learning methods was found effective. Digital tools were found to facilitate the collaboration and to encourage the transition towards circular practices. Moreover, digital options offer participants the possibility to learn at its own rhythm, at any time and place. However, the interactive approach is based on the partnership between public and private institutes (Türkeli and Schophuizen, 2019).

The third objective of this paper is to illustrate the relationship between education and circular economy, Figure 3. Undoubtedly, all targets of the SDG are critical for the sustainable development. However, we will focus on certain targets.

Responsible consumption, as part of SDG 12, is a requirement of the circular economy. Principles of the circular economy are elimination of waste and pollution, regeneration of nature and circularity of products and materials (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). These are expressed by target 5 of the SDG 12: "By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse". However, as it was discussed by scholars, these actions involve responsible consumers because they have to return the products. Consumers are prepared to return products only if they are aware of the benefits. Therefore target 5 of SDG 12, is directly influenced by target 8 of SDG 12: "By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature".

Moreover, a precondition of awareness and information existence is education. This builds a habitat where the circular economy can prosper. Individuals have to be educated from the role of the worker and citizen. Target 4 of SDG 4 refers to the position of the employee: "By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship". By having relevant skills and decent jobs, employees are motivated to engage in sustainable development. Companies have to invest in quality education methods for the staff to have knowledge in the circular economy (Schroeder, Anggraeni and Weber, 2019). Likewise, entrepreneurship can develop innovative technologies, which can help with interactive learning methods. Target 5 of SDG 12 that individuals is presence of skills, abilities, and capacities.

Similarly, the individual's position of engaged citizenship has an influence on SDG 12, target 8. Information and awareness can prosper only if the consumer acknowledge cultural diversity and peace because these are indicators of a united society. In this manner, consumers put aside individual benefits in favor of collective good and adapt a sustainable lifestyle.

Figure 3. The framework of the relationship between targets of SDG12 and SDG4

Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic marks the beginning of a new era. Old challenges become more prominent and new mentalities arise. It is important to create a strong foundation in circular economy education in order to successfully implement to deal with the challenges that the future holds (Ambrus et al., 2018; Taucean et al., 2019). At the basis of implementing the closed-loop concept, information needs to be provided and awareness has to be raised. Sustainability and the circular economy must become a normality for all individuals (Cioca et al., 2019). Through this way, consumer can adapt responsible behavior.

Among the respondents an average level of knowledge was identified. Looking at the involvement level, we can draw the conclusion that individuals in Romania desire to have a circular behavior. These results reveal that there is interest, but also lack of education.

In terms of efficient education models, it has been identified that circular economy education models have to be interactive, adapted to the field of learning and based on collaboration between public and private institutions. Also, interactive methods such as games or digital tool have been proven successful. Furthermore, the respondents' involvement level can be categorized based on generation. Education models should consider which generation they are addressed to.

Last but not least, this study illustrated the relationship between targets of SDG 12 and SDG 4. Responsible consumption can be achieved only if consumer is informed and aware of the sustainable development and lifestyle. However, this implies that the consumer is educated as a worker and as a citizenship to behave responsible.

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